

THE ELECTRON-SPECTROSCOPIC INVESTIGATIONS OF THE EPITAXIAL CoSi_2 FILMS ON SILICON

Abstract. This work is devoted to the study of the electronic structure, optical properties and electric resistance of the epitaxial layers CoSi_2/Si produced in the ultrahigh vacuum conditions ($p=10^{-7}$ Pa) by the molecular beam epitaxy method on Si surface (111). It has been shown that the forbidden zone width of solid CoSi_2 films is 0.5-0.6 eV and there are two maximal of the electron state density in the valence zone. These films have the low specific resistance ($\rho=20-25 \mu\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$).

Keywords silicon, epitaxial, structure, vacuum, electron, zone, temperature, spectroscopy, CoSi_2 , molecular beam epitaxy method, electron-spectroscopic, silicid, peaks, spectra, films.

1. INTRODUCTION.

The good structural concordance of Si , CoSi_2 , CaF_2 and hence the growing of multi-layer systems from the layers of those materials combination are the first prerequisite to create devices with unique specifications. The creation of the $\text{Si-CoSi}_2\text{-Si}$ epitaxial structure allows the manufacturing of new type of ultrahigh frequency devices, e.g., transistors with metallic and permeable base. The main principle of such transistors creating is based on the change of the semiconductor base to the material having low electric resistance close to the metal one. In this respect, the more suitable material proved to be CoSi_2 films [1-4].

By now the regularities of the CoSi_2 film epitaxial growth on the Si single crystal surface have been studied. The optimal conditions of producing the uniform films have been determined, the type and parameters of the lattice, as well as the electric physical properties of these films have been investigated.

In the article the results of epitaxial $\text{CoSi}_2 / \text{Si}$ (111) formed by MBE, TFE and RA. Cobalt silicide layers grown on substrates such as Si doped by phosphorus-4,5, Si doped by boron -7.5, Si doped by boron -10. The growth of the films produced in ultrahigh vacuum MBE installation. Before epitaxial growth surface of the substrates were subjected to chemical cleaning and special cleaning vacuum. Detailed description of the installation of the MBE and purification methods contained in [5]. The thickness of the deposited cobalt in all cases was 100 Å, meanwhile, CoSi_2 film with thickness about 380 Å was formed. The one-

step processes were studied and a two-step growth. With two-stage increase in the growth of the film took place in two stages with different modes of growth.

This work is devoted to the study of the electronic structure, optimal properties and electric resistance of the epitaxial $CoSi_2/Si$ layers produced in the ultrahigh vacuum conditions ($p=10^{-7}$ Pa) by the molecular beam epitaxial method on Si surface (111). The optimal growth temperature is $T=850$ K and the optimal ratio of flows $SiCo$ is 2: 1. The films of the thickness $d=50-500$ Å have been studied [5].

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Before the measurement of the $CoSi_2$ films were annealed in the ultrahigh vacuum conditions ($p=10^{-7}$ Pa) at $T=900-1000$ K for 3-4 hours. After the treatment on the HEED pictures taken for the films with $d>150$ Å the bright sharp point reflexes on Laue arcs were detected, that corresponds to the pure atomic smooth surfaces.

The photoelectrons spectra for the Si (111) and $CoSi_2$ films ($d=200$ Å) measured at $h\nu=10.8$ eV are given in fig. 1.

Fig 1. The photoelectrons spectra for the Si (111) and $CoSi_2$ films ($d=200$ Å) measured at $h\nu=10.8$ eV.

The abscissa axis is the electron binding energy E_b taken relative to the Fermi level E_F . It is seen that the shape and position of the main peaks for Si and silicide are visible distinguished from each other. In the pure Si case the presence of peaks (B, C, E) is explained by the electron excitation from $3p$, $3s$ states of valence electrons and from the surface states.

The parameters of the energy zones for Si and $CoSi_2$ defined according to the photoelectron spectra (fig.1) are given in table 1.

Table 1

Sample	Zone parameters, eV				
	ϕ	φ	E_g	χ	V_s
Si	5.1	4.7	1.1	4.0	0.3
$CoSi_2$	4.9	4.9	0.5	4.4	—

Table 1. Zone and energy parameters of Si and $CoSi_2$.

It can be seen from table I that from Si to $CoSi_2$ the decreasing (2 times) of the forbidden zone width E_g , the straightening of the zone band and some increasing of the electron affinity value occur.

The value of the both photoelectron ϕ and thermo electron φ work functions for Si and $CoSi_2$ do not sharp differ from each other. For $CoSi_2$ $F \approx \varphi$. So it can be

supposed that $CoSi_2$ is the degenerated semiconductor with the whole conductivity. The high electric conductivity of Co silicide can be due to this fact.

The electric resistance of the $CoSi_2$ films was defined by the 4-probes method [6]. The experimental result had been showed that in the case of the very thin films ($d > 100 \text{ \AA}$) the specific resistance value depends on both thickness and temperature of the film formation and in the solid films case ($d > 100-150 \text{ \AA}$) it depends mainly, on the formation temperature. The value of ρ for the $CoSi_2$ films growing at the different T are given in table 2.

So for the film width $d \approx 60 \text{ \AA}$ the value of ρ becomes higher and even at the optimal formation temperatures it is about $120-150 \mu\Omega.cm$. That is mainly due to the fact that the film is not solid. The solid films ($d \approx 200 \text{ \AA}$) growing at $T < 700-750 \text{ K}$ also have the high resistance. This fact is explained by insufficient ordering of the structure and by the high density of the point defects.

Table 2.

T, K	$\rho, \mu\Omega.cm$	
	$d \approx 60 \text{ \AA}$	$d \approx 200 \text{ \AA}$
600	250	110
750	–	50
900	150	20
1000	120	20
1100	–	40
1200	120	70

Table 2. The dependence of ρ on the temperature formation for $CoSi_2$.

The temperature increases of the film growth up to $900-1000 \text{ K}$ results the sharp ρ decreasing ($20-25 \mu\Omega.cm$), that is connected with the essential crystal perfection improvement of $CoSi_2$ film. The further formation temperature increases ($T > 1100 \text{ K}$) is accompanied by the specific resistance increasing. That can be due to both the island film formation and the enrichment of the surface with silicon owing to silicon diffusion through the film.

The optical properties of $CoSi_2/Si(100)$ films have been also studied. For the example the dependence of the light reflection coefficient on the light wave length for the 200 \AA thickness film is given in Fig.2. It was shown that within the whole studied range of light wave length λ the k value increases with the λ increasing.

However, for $\lambda < 2-2.5 \mu$ the increasing is small and its value do not exceed $10-15\%$. The considerable k increasing occurs beginning with $\lambda = 2.5 \mu$, that approximately coincides with the edge of fundamental absorption $CoSi_2$. At $\lambda > 2.5 \mu$ the $h\nu$ value becomes less than the forbidden zone width ($E_g \approx 0.5 \text{ eV}$) of $CoSi_2$ and

Fig 2. The dependence of the light reflection coefficient on the light wave length for the 200 Å thickness film hence the absorption coefficient sharply decreases. Apparently, that results in some increasing of the light reflection coefficient.

3. CONCLUSIONS.

1. The true information about the electron states density distribution in the valence zone and the energy parameters for $CoSi_2/Si$ films has been obtained.

2. It was shown that the electric resistance of $CoSi_2$ film produced by the molecular beam epitaxy method mainly depends on the thickness and temperature of the film formation. $CoSi_2$ is supposed to be a degenerated semiconductor with whole conductivity. High electric conductivity of Co silicide is explained by that fact.

3. The considerable increasing of the light reflection coefficient beginning with $\lambda=2-2.5 \mu$ was explained by the inter-zone transitions absence (fundamental absorption) in $CoSi_2$ at $\lambda>2-2.5 \mu$.

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